

Use of Alumina as Ion Exchanger in the Separation of Carrier free ^{90}Y from ^{90}Sr

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Radiochemical separation of carrier free ^{90}Y from ^{90}Sr has been carried out in presence of 1M ammonium chloride solution, by adsorbing ^{90}Y in powdered alumina column. ^{90}Y was later washed out quantitatively, with conc. hydrochloric acid. Study of the beta decay half life of the separated product proved beyond doubt that the isotope is radiochemically pure. Overall separation procedure took less than one hour.

SEPARATION of ^{90}Y in a carrier-free state from its mother ^{90}Sr had been a problem for long time. Needs are often felt for the highest possible sensitivity in ^{90}Y measurements where carrier separation is undesirable because carrier could decrease the effective counting efficiency of the emitted β particles. In case of fission product or fall out sample, ^{90}Sr is stored for ingrowth of ^{90}Y and then fed and adsorbed in Dowex-50 column^{1,2}, wherefrom ^{90}Y milked off and ^{90}Sr was later washed out with citric acid at different pH. Milking of ^{90}Y from a Dowex-50X8 column using lactate and glycolate solutions at various pH was also studied and compared³.

Solvent extractions⁴⁻⁶, formation of radiocolloidal yttrium in basic solution⁷, zone technique similar to ascending paper chromatography⁸ have been claimed to be good methods. Methods like electrolytic deposition, electrochromatography, mass spectrometry and vacuum evaporation however involve number of steps, time consuming and were of complicated nature.

Ion exchange column such as Dowex-1 pretreated with hydroxide^{9,10} and nitrate with some 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid¹¹, electro dialysis of EDTA complex using membranes of anion exchanger¹² and use of some cation exchanger in methanol ammonium acetate medium¹³ have been however utilised in better way. Columns of titanium and zirconium phosphates in either hydrogen or ammonium form¹⁴, and of ammonium phosphomolybdate¹⁵ have been also used. In spite of above mentioned several processes, searches for establishing a standard, quick and quantitative yield-giving separation method for obtaining carrier free ^{90}Y are still being carried out by several workers.

Chromatographic alumina due to its unique adsorption character, acid, radiation and temperature resistant properties, has been described^{16,17} for sometimes for the successful separation of carrier free daughter activities from their respective parents like ^{99}Mo - ^{99}Tc ,¹⁸ ^{140}Ba - ^{140}La ,¹⁹ ^{144}Ce - ^{144}Pm ,²⁰ ^{210}Pb -

^{210}Bi ,²¹ pairs. Alumina column was therefore chosen for the separation of ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y mixture, and an attempt has been made by utilising a very simple chemical procedure, described below.

Experimental

^{90}Sr activity in equilibrium with ^{90}Y was supplied as chloride by AERE, Harwell, England. Carrier free ^{90}Y activity was procured from BARC, Trombay, India. Chromatographic alumina was of G.R.E. Merck quality. All other reagents and acids used in the investigations were of AnalaR grade.

A glass column (25×1 cm) was prepared, and packed with 16 g of aluminium oxide, which was plugged with glass wool both at the top and at the bottom. The eluate was collected in a conical flask connected to a water pump which regulated the flow of solution to a rate of 14-15 drops/min.

For the study of extent of adsorption of ^{90}Y on alumina definite amounts of tracer solution were taken at different pH ranges from 2 to 9 in different L shaped tubes, mixed with weighed quantity (1 g) of alumina and shaken in a thermostat at room temperature till the equilibrium is reached, and relative adsorptions were studied by measuring the activity remained in the solutions. The effect of other salt solution medium like NH_4Cl , NaCl , and KCl on the adsorption of ^{90}Y over alumina was similarly followed.

The extent of desorption was studied by pouring the activity solution in the alumina column and then washing separately with hydrochloric and nitric acids of different molarities. For the separation of carrier free ^{90}Y from ^{90}Sr , equilibrium solution was evaporated to dryness, taken up with water, adjusted to the predetermined pH (~5) for ^{90}Y desorption, and then fed into the column. Presuming maximum amount of ^{90}Y has been adsorbed, strontium activity was eluted out by washing with 1M ammonium

chloride solution. ^{90}Y activity was later washed out by 28 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid solution, and collected in the receiver. 10 ml of this solution was then counted in a beta type liquid counter. The overall separation took less than 1 hr. Experiment was repeated by using sodium chloride as washing agent for strontium activity, which however indicated no recordable change.

Results and Discussions

Study on the extent of ^{90}Y adsorption showed that the adsorption of the activity over alumina increases with rise of pH upto 5, and then decreases with further increase of pH , whereas the adsorption of strontium steadily increases from pH 2 to pH 9 (Table 1). It was found that in presence of the alkali

TABLE 1—K VALUES OF ^{90}Sr AND ^{90}Y AT DIFFERENT pH

pH values	^{90}Sr	^{90}Y
2	0	2
3	4	5
4	56	33
5	280	700
6	305	650
7	375	450
8	430	100
9	680	10

metal salt solution ^{90}Sr does not adsorb in the alumina column and no ^{90}Y could be detected in the first washing solution of the column. Batch distribution study with ^{90}Sr (separated from ^{90}Y by adding strontium as hold back carrier) was also carried out at different pH values, and the adsorption coefficient K was calculated from the following expression :

$$K = \frac{\text{activity per gram of the adsorbent}}{\text{activity per ml of the solution}}$$

Fig. 1. Elution curve of ^{90}Y carried down through alumina column with different HCl concentrations.

and then compared with those calculated for ^{90}Y adsorption.

Yttrium was thus found to adsorb in the column at its solution pH 5, and the strontium retained along-with was later washed down with 1M NH_4Cl (50 ml of eluent is sufficient). It was also observed that at pH 9 where strontium adsorption is maximum, yttrium came down only with very low yield, a fact however was not observed in the batch operation experiment with ^{90}Y activity alone.

The study of desorption of ^{90}Y from the alumina column showed that desorption of the activity increases with the concentration of hydrochloric acid. Desorption is minimum with 1M , fair with 6M and complete with only 28 ml of 12M HCl (Fig. 1), and hydrochloric acid was proved to be more efficient than nitric acid for such study. The collected hydrochloric acid washing solution was evaporated to small volume which did not show any solid alumina particle, was then measured for ^{90}Y . The beta decay curve of ^{90}Y (Fig. 2) showed that the separated product is of high radiochemical purity.

Fig. 2. Decay curve of ^{90}Y separated from ^{90}Sr .

Above study indicated the possibility of the use of chromatographic alumina for similar chemical separation problems.

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